

Table 2. Bunt- and false smut-infected grains on affected panicles of different cultivars, Assam, India, 1965.

Cultivar	Bunt-infected grain (%)	False smut-infected grain (%)
TN1	39.71	—
Unknown	22.34	—
Unknown	1.36	1.49
Unknown	26.32	0.11
Hsinchu 2	10.42	—
Unknown	—	2.01

represent the total field population (on individual panicles bunt varied from 8 to 63% and false smut, 18 to 79% in 1964). ■

Hypersensitive reaction induced by *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the cowpea leaf

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Lesion development due to virulent strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* on rice leaves was remarkably inhibited by both mixing and preinoculation treatments with an avirulent or weakly virulent mutant strain in experiments conducted at the IRRI greenhouse. But no inhibitory effect was observed when the virulent strain was inoculated before the avirulent or weakly virulent strains.

All efforts have failed to induce a hypersensitive reaction (HR) by combining a resistant rice variety and the *X. oryzae* strain. But cowpea was found to be a suitable indicator for HR induction. HR was rapidly induced by both virulent wild strains exemplified by different virulence groups and by virulent induced mutants. Only living cells of bacteria could induce HR, and critical numbers for induction seemed to be $2-5 \times 10^6$ cells/ml. None of heat-killed bacterial cells, cell-free supernatants, or polysaccharide fraction prepared from the bacterial culture induced HR. On the other hand, avirulent strains either delayed HR or did not induce it at all. ■

Resistance to bacterial blight

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Rice cultivars were screened for resistance to bacterial blight disease. The plants were raised in pots containing wetland soil and in the field spaced 20 x 10 cm. Fertilizers were applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. The plants were inoculated at three stages: seedling (20 days), tillering (50 days), and boot-leaf. The disease severity was scored on a scale of 0-9. Many cultivars were rated susceptible; a few were moderately resistant.

Interestingly, ASD5 was resistant,

Reaction of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial blight disease.

Variety or culture	Disease severity scale ^a					
	Seedling		Tillering		Boot-leaf	
	Pots	Field	Pots	Field	Pots	Field
BJ1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sigadis	0	0	0	0	1	0
TKM6	1	0	1	0	1	1
ASD5	1	0	1	1	5	5
IR22	1	1	5	3	5	5
IR26	3	1	5	5	5	5
Pankaj	1	1	3	1	3	3
TN1	5	5	7	7	7	7
TNAU7124 (ASD5/IR22)	1	1	1	1	5	3
TNAU15776 (IR20/ASD5)	1	1	1	1	5	3
ASD15 (IR22/IR26)	3	3	7	7	7	7

^a0 = not affected, 9 = highly susceptible.

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at AICRIP, India

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To determine possible strains of tungro virus and biotypes of tungro vectors in various localities, the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* collected and reared locally were tested on seedlings of 10 rice varieties in

comparable with TKM6 until tillering. IR22 and IR26 were moderately susceptible and ASD5 was resistant in the tillering stage. But ASD5 became infected in the panicle-emergence stage. Progeny of ASD5—TNAU7124 and TNAU15776 — also scored resistant until tillering and were moderately susceptible in the boot-leaf stage. The contribution of resistance by IR22 and IR20 in those two cultivars appears insufficient. ASD15 (IR22/IR26) is also susceptible (see table).

ASD5 has potential resistance until the tillering stage to the bacterium strain that causes severe damage to most of the improved rice varieties known to be bacterial-blight resistant. ■

the AICRIP greenhouse, Rajendranagar, India, 12-30 September 1978. Two hundred adult insects, 10 females and 10 males for each variety, were given an acquisition access time of 3 days on tungro-diseased plants. The insects survived 1 to 18 days on 1-week-old seedlings. Their average life span was 4.6 days (5.0 days for female insects and 4.2 days for the male).

When the average life span was used to indicate the effect of rice variety on the insect, Gam Pai 30-12-15, IR34, Ptb 18, and Ambemohar 159 showed more resistance to the insect than Habiganj

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Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at AICRIP, India, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
TN1	18	6.4 a	95	4	1.8	37	1.60	1.68
IR26	7	5.6 ab	80	3	1.4	26	1.10	1.38
Habiganj DW8	8	5.2 ab	80	3	1.4	35	1.15	1.44
Pankhari 203	14	4.8 bc	75	2	1.1	22	0.80	1.07
Latisail	8	4.8 bc	75	3	2.2	30	1.25	1.67
Kataribhog	8	4.8 bc	75	2	1.3	24	1.00	1.33
Ambemohar 159	8	4.2 cd	85	3	1.6	38	1.40	1.65
Ptb 18	8	3.7 cd	85	2	1.5	40	1.25	1.47
IR34	8	3.7 cd	70	1	1.0	22	0.70	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	8	2.8 d	75	1	1.0	27	0.75	1.00
Max or av	18	4.6	80	4	1.4	30	1.10	1.37

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

DW8, IR26, and TN1 (see table).

About 30% of 729 seedlings inoculated by the viruliferous insects became infected. There seemed to be no remarkable differences among the 10 rice varieties as far as tungro transmission was concerned. However, the insects were

less efficient in transmitting the tungro virus to IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and Pankhari 203 than to the other varieties (see table). Those three might be more resistant to tungro than the others in the test. ■

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at IRRI, Philippines

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As part of the RTV Collaborative Project, an IRRI study investigated the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* in the IRRI greenhouse from 15 May to 28 June, 1978. In two

trials, 800 adult insects — 40 females and 40 males on 10 varieties — were given an acquisition access time of 4 days on tungro-diseased seedlings. The insects survived 1 to 23 days. The average life span was 4.8 days (5.0 days for female insects, and 4.6 days for the male).

The short life span on IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Ptb 18, and Pankhari 203 indicated that these varieties were more resistant to the insect than were the six others in the test (see table).

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at IRRI, Philippines, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
Habiganj DW8	23	7.3 a	14	1	1.0	3	0.14	1.00
Kataribhog	14	7.2 a	18	2	1.2	4	0.19	1.07
IR26	12	5.9 b	81	4	1.6	31	1.24	1.52
TN1	15	5.7 b	89	4	1.5	36	1.28	1.44
Ambemohar 159	19	5.5 b	48	3	1.2	16	0.56	1.18
Latisail	13	5.4 b	71	5	1.5	27	0.99	1.39
Pankhari 203	11	3.8 c	5	2	1.3	2	0.05	1.00
Ptb 18	9	2.6 d	45	2	1.0	18	0.45	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	6	2.6 d	48	2	1.0	20	0.49	1.03
IR34	6	2.3 d	54	2	1.0	25	0.55	1.02
Max or av	23	4.8	47	5	1.5	18	0.60	1.17

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Of 2,637 seedlings of 10 rice varieties inoculated by the insects, 18% developed tungro. Insect efficiency in transmitting the tungro virus was lowest with Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, and Kataribhog. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Anatomical studies of rice varieties tolerant of and susceptible to complete submergence at seedling stage

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Leaf sheath and leaf blades from 12 varieties were collected in 10-day-old seedlings to study the anatomical differences between varieties tolerant of the susceptible to complete submergence.

The number of vascular bundles on the first and second leaf blades varied among the varieties; however, the difference between the tolerant and susceptible varieties was not significant.

The leaf sheath is characterized by the presence of a large air space which alternates with the vascular bundles and is separated by narrow bands of parenchyma. The number of vascular bundles in the first and second leaf sheaths of the tolerant and susceptible varieties did not show any difference or correlation to submergence tolerance.

The role of the air space in submergence has not been studied. It possibly is important because it may serve as an oxygen reservoir or, if the leaf tips are above the water level, as passageway for transporting oxygen from the leaf blade to the roots. Thus, the air space might play an important role in maintaining the integrity of the cells. On the other hand, the occurrence of large air spaces may result in spongy, weak leaf sheaths that would make the plant prone to lodging when the water level recedes.

The percentage of air space per unit area was negatively and significantly correlated to submergence tolerance ($r = -0.5997^*$). The air spaces on the first leaf